

ESTIMATING BIKE USAGE AND IMPROVING REPAIR SHOP OPERATIONS IN BYKE SHARING SYSTEMS

Bursoo Brahma Teja¹, Ankam Arun Raj², Kuruva Praveen Kumar³, Mr. L. Suneel⁴

^{1,2,3} UG Student, Dept. of ECE, CMR Institute of Technology, Hyderabad

⁴ Assistant Professor, Dept. of ECE,

CMR Institute of Technology, Hyderabad

ABSTRACT

Supply chain responsiveness and big data analytics (BDA) have garnered considerable interest in academia and among practitioners. BDA helps researchers understand the current challenges in data management, including the high volume, velocity, and variety of data. This study is concerned with improving the responsiveness of supply chain networks to bike-sharing systems (BSS), which exhibit BDA characteristics. To address the challenges of forecasting bike usage and accordingly optimizing repair shop operations, we analyze multi-factor BSS data (Data from Washington D.C. BSS available to public), wherein attributes, such as weather conditions, registration, humidity, date, and time, are present. We use machine learning algorithms, such as neural networks, decision-tree-based regression, K-nearest neighbor, support vectors, and ensemble random forest, to predict bike usage and repair. This work contests the results and demonstrates the effectiveness of combining machine learning with supply chain network design. Supply chain networks model bike repairs by means of capacity extensions, which entails a nonlinear problem. In this study, we utilize a gradient search to solve a nonlinear supply chain network model. By enabling capacity extension, bike repair shops within the BSS exhibit a promising 50 % reduction in lead repair time. Furthermore, a 25 % overall throughput increase in BSS is achieved. Ultimately, this study demonstrates the importance of operational flexibility in responding to big data challenges.

INTRODUCTION

Changes are taking place in the future development of the transport sector. To this aim, concrete plans are already in place, such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [1], the New Urban Agenda [2] and the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Greening Transport [3], and adopted by United Nations member states since 2016.

To cope with these challenges, the New Urban Agenda and OECD Greening Transport set up the guidelines for a sustainable future that connects to the SDG11 Cities and Communities [4].

Bike-sharing systems (BSS) improve urban accessibility, multimodality in transportation and mobility sustainability, and more cities in the world are implementing such sharing modes to tackle increased expansion of urban mobility, air pollution and changes in urban mobility patterns and behaviour, trends exacerbated by the recent pandemic crisis.

Since 2016, more than 1000 bike-sharing systems are running in 60 countries [5], and many improvements have been made in bike-sharing systems. The latest systems allow real-time data collection using sensors and wireless communications, generating large quantities of data [6]. The collected data improve intelligent processes of data analytics through machine learning techniques. The aim of this paper is to contribute, with literature evidence, to the sustainable implementation of bike-sharing systems. Particularly, this systematic literature review targets the identification of the most relevant machine learning techniques applied in bike-sharing analytics, with an impact on and contributions to cities' mobility. Therefore, the broad analysis of this paper is useful to understand state-of-the-art solutions, as well as gaps in the current research.

Challenges in mobility nowadays aim to find the latest scientific contributions for the development of machine-learning-based techniques to provide solutions to tackle cities' mobility phenomenon, particularly when dealing with bike-sharing systems. Based on the general overview described above, our study provides a systematic literature review (SLR) on this topic. The SLR research question was formulated as follows:

RQ1: What are the most promising machine learning techniques adopted by the community to better understand and improve bike-sharing systems in urban mobility?

To answer this question, an SLR methodology and qualitative analysis were used, as well as methods to assist in analysing the data

EXISTING SYSTEM

Using Google Scholar, Science Direct, ProQuest, and Engineering Village, we searched for Mixed-Integer Programming (MIP) general models that address challenges in the management of BSS. We initially reviewed general BSS, without reference to maintenance, big data, machine learning in predictive demand analytics, supply chain management, or flexible supply chain models. The service level requirements of bike-docking stations have been frequently explored in the literature. The general allocation of bikes to dock stations is the most common theme in existing studies ([2], [21], [37], [41], [44], [59], [60], [66]). In a typical BSS service-level problem, there is a trade-off between attaining a high customer level (availability of bikes at any time), and the costs of allocating bikes to stations and purchasing a large inventory of bikes. Generally, optimally placing

bike-docking stations and repositioning bikes can reduce the routing costs for trucks, which replenish and reposition bikes. In showcasing this theme, Freund et al. [21] examined the number of docks used for each station, bike rebalancing among stations, and expansion planning. The authors applied mathematical programming to achieve an optimal solution by relying on a careful statistical analysis of the data. Collini et al. [13] introduce a predictive methodology and solution for short-term predictions, given available BSS's bikes, smart stations and three months data. They utilize Ensemble and Deep Learning solutions.

Ashqar et al. [6] introduce a BSS model that applies machine learning at the level of the network and stations. They use Random Forest and Least-Squares Boosting as univariate regression to model the number of available bike stations. Bustamante et al. [9] employ multiple machine learning algorithms using probabilistic programming through Bayesian inference. Their work study the impact of COVID 19 on ridership. Ngo et al. [40] use Random Forest (RF) and k-fold to predict the hourly demand of bikes in the city of Seoul (Korea) using information related to rental hour, temperature, humidity, visibility, wind speed, dew-point, snowfall, solar radiation, and rainfall. Zhou et al. [69] develop a novel approach of prediction and optimization where optimization and branch-and-price algorithms are used. Their method saves significant costs (operational costs) and reduce the waste of resources. Overall, studies pertaining to this theme are abundant; however, when we supplemented repair/maintenance with our search criteria, we discovered a noticeable gap in research. Even though one of the important aspects of BSS is maintenance, literature pertaining to that aspect is scarce. This could be because numerous cities outsource maintenance to third-party organizations. However, repair and maintenance are indirect costs that are eventually reflected in BSS cost structures. Furthermore, some cities do manage the repair and maintenance of bikes within their BSS [52]. Big data is intrinsic in BSS because the underlying data structure features all three of its basic features: high volume, high variety, and high velocity. Because BSS are typically installed in large urban centers, data from BSS depositories feature an immense amount of information [76] as the users average in the thousands, if not the millions. Furthermore, numerous attributes, such as user characteristics (registration status, student status, gender, etc.), trip information (GPS tracking, mileage, and maintenance issues), and external characteristics (weather, humidity, holidays, etc.), are highly variable. In addition, high velocity is associated with rapid changes in the data. Most available data structures provide readings on an hourly, or occasionally per-minute, basis. The BSS literature is rich in studies that emphasize big data ([21], [34], [37],

[41], [44], [59], [60], [62], [63], [68]). Zhao et al. [68] examined weather variations to develop a comprehensive model for inferring the relationship between weather variability and cycling. Alternatively, coupling BSS with machine learning has provided a large volume of research. Ashqar et al. [5] studied the availability of bikes at docking stations using random forest (RF) and least-squares boosting. Wang and Kim [55] proposed short-term forecasting for docking stations in Suzhou, China, by means of long short-term memory (LSTM) and gated recurrent units (GRU). They used random forest as a benchmark to test their performance. Singhvi et al. [50] utilized a linear regression model to predict bike demand in New York City. Arque [4] utilized random forest to forecast bike demand. Liu et al. [35] introduced an LSTM model to forecast the number of bikes over multiple time steps. All authors in question reinforced their contributions based on the significance of their practical implications. With the aid of this research, bike-sharing agencies can make better decisions regarding the distribution of bikes to docking stations. Within the context of SCM, Raviv and Koka [43] conducted a study that analyzes the inventory management of bikes at each station, and proposed an inventory model for the management of these stations, where a numerical solution was presented. Most importantly, they indicated that fluctuations are the biggest challenge in the management of bike-sharing systems. Li et al. [31] reviewed the impact of important factors, such as price, traffic congestion, and supply chain, on bike-sharing selection behavior. They utilized big data to evaluate bike-sharing apps in Beijing over a 4-d period. Unlike that on machine learning applications and service-level bike allocations, research on SCM in the context of BSS is scarce. Adding flexibility to the search criterion yielded negative results. To the best of our knowledge, no existing study considers flexible supply chain networks within the context of BSS.

DISADVANTAGES

- The K-nearest neighbor (KNN) algorithm is not used in which a non-parametric algorithm that has been used for classification and regression problems.
- The main distinct feature of a support vector machine (SVM) is not used in which the use of a hyper plane that discriminates between classes of data.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

To synthesize the motivation of the paper, we design a supply chain network consisting of demand nodes (bike docks), repair shops, and suppliers for the procurement of bikes' parts. At the demand side, we utilize multiple machine learning algorithms to predict the demand of bikes needing repair. This translates to demand input in the supply chain network. The repair shops are flexible and can

extend their repair capacities by crashing operational resources. Hence, the repair shops respond to the demanded repairs at the bike docks. Further, the model integrates the transportation costs all through the supply chain. Since the repair of bikes in a BSS is a must for sustaining acceptable service levels, the model supplies decision makers (city planners) with fundamental operational characteristics for optimal service levels and operational costs.

ADVANTAGES

- First, the introduction of flexible operations, via the use of capacity extension, brings promising results in overall responsiveness to the repair needs of the BSS. Second, the artificial neural network algorithm tend to bring the lowest prediction error when compared with the rest of the algorithms, at a mean error of less than 1 percent of the actual value. Third, the combination of demand analytics and supply chain modeling produces 25% throughput improvement in the overall model.
- The main scope of this study is cutting-edge machine learning techniques combined with an optimization model to better manage and coordinate supply chain operations in response to demand fluctuations. It is important to first discuss the nature of the data in question. The first part of this section discusses the scope of this study. The rest is devoted to machine learning algorithms – the algorithms used to navigate and make sense of data.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Bike-sharing systems are growing in importance, and are being implemented in most cities with high urban densities. These systems may financially exhaust cities owing to the costs of bike maintenance and repositioning. This study illustrated the effectiveness of flexible repair services in managing the maintenance of bikes. High usage of bikes in BSS results in wear-and-tear and possible misuse of bikes. Repair and general maintenance are therefore necessary to control the overall operating cost of a BSS. Our model demonstrated that flexible repair plants can respond quickly to demand spikes. In contrast, in the parallel nonflexible model, this reaction was slower. The accurate prediction of bike usage is a challenging task. Some latent factors are present in BSS because of consumer behavioral changes. This study investigated these factors and demonstrated the effectiveness of neural networks. Deep learning tends to extract patterns that are latent and

unidentifiable using classical algorithms. The coupling of demand data analytics and supply chain modeling produces higher synchronization between maintenance and usage. Repair shops that can quickly extend their capacity can serve as playbooks for best practices. Our results show unique operational characteristics that contrast certain repair shops, which in turn can be imitated and implemented. For practitioners, demand analytics provides accurate predictions based on given weather conditions. The data used in this study provide multiple relevant features, such as temperature, humidity, wind speed, and season. Given specific temperature, wind speed, and humidity dynamics, our model can predict the bike demand with good accuracy. This is quite important as decision makers have access to reliable weather forecasts. Therefore, demand prediction can be relayed to repair facilities so that operational adjustments can be carried out. Naturally, flexible shops that can quickly extend operational capacity would benefit most from these predictions. The work incorporates flexible operations, via the use of capacity extension. Our results supply a repair leadtime reduction higher than 50%. While the coupling of demand analytics and supply chain modeling produces a 25% throughput improvement in the overall model. On the demand analytics side, we see a huge advantage of the neural network algorithm, which delivered predictions that are higher than 99% in accuracy. Given some limitations of this work, there are some important future research opportunities. First, this study focused on docked BSS's, wherein designated stations are built and maintained. Because dockless BSS's are predominant and growing in popularity, future studies could examine maintenance issues with respect to dockless bikes. Furthermore, the demand behavior becomes more cumbersome for dockless systems, and it may be interesting to evaluate the performance of the proposed machine-learning algorithms in such a setting. On the supply chain side, we can look at location allocation problem [78] in the context of BSS.

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